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Perpetrating Narrative: The Ethics of Unreliable Narration in *The Act of Killing*

Abstract

This article analyses the ethics of unreliable narration in Oppenheimer's 2012 documentary *The Act of Killing*, in which perpetrators of the 1965-1966 Indonesian massacres of supposed communists reenact their crimes. By showing the perpetrators' gleeful depictions of their murderous histories, Oppenheimer breaks with numerous conventions of representing genocidal perpetrators to spectacular effect and much critical controversy. The documentary relies on a sophisticated toolset to expose the perpetrators' narratives as unreliable. I argue that the unreliability we encounter in the film is not focused on the axis of facts, as many critics discussing the supposed fictionality of the reenactments contend, but on the axes of perception and, most importantly, ethics. The conventions of representing genocidal perpetrators have been formed in post-genocidal contexts in which the perpetrators have been condemned (most dominantly the Holocaust), but in Indonesia these perpetrators still wield power with impunity. This circumstance demanded a new filmic approach. I argue that *The Act of Killing* exposes the perpetrators as unreliable narrators in an Indonesian socio-political context that celebrates them and shows the deeply troubling ethics of these narratives.

Keywords: unreliable narration, genocide, Indonesian 1965–1966 massacres, documentary, Oppenheimer, *The Act of Killing*

Joshua Oppenheimer's film *The Act of Killing* (2012; hereafter TAOK) breaks with numerous conventions of documentaries on genocide to spectacular effect. In the 2012 film, several perpetrators of the 1965–1966 Indonesian massacres of more than 500,000 communists, feminists, union members, and ethnic Chinese direct reenactments of their killings.¹ Oppenheimer, in turn, films the making-of of the reenactments. Instead of focusing on the victims, a tradition instituted particularly by documentary representations of the Holocaust,² the film focuses on the perpetrators.³ It also breaks with (the relatively few) established conventions of representing genocidal perpetrators in documentary by not representing these perpetrators in a judicial context or in confrontation with victims' resentment.⁴ Finally and perhaps the film's most arresting quality is the perpetrators' cinematically styled-up reenactments which blatantly flout conventions of "verisimilitude"⁵ and "factual authority,"⁶ so often and fervently demanded of works about genocide, and fly in the face of Western documentary traditions asserting the truthfulness of testimony and reenactment-as-testimony.⁷ TAOK's challenging the reliability of perpetrators' testimonies and reenactments and its ethical implications for perpetrator representation is what I will examine here.

¹ On the history of these killings, see Geoffrey Robinson, *The Killing Season: A History of the Indonesian Massacres, 1965-66*, Human Rights and Crimes against Humanity (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2018); Jess Melvin, *The Army and the Indonesian Genocide: Mechanics of Mass Murder* (New York: Routledge, 2018).

² Rebecca Jinks, *Representing Genocide: The Holocaust as Paradigm?* (London: Bloomsbury, 2016), 23–24.

³ Originally Oppenheimer attempted to focus on the victims, but because of difficulties and dangers to the victims he decided to shift focus on the perpetrators instead. After TAOK Oppenheimer also directed a film focused on the victims: Joshua Oppenheimer, *The Look of Silence*, Documentary (Dogwoof, 2014).

⁴ See Morag's examination of Cambodian documentaries on genocide—which themselves are unusual relative to Western representations of genocide (especially the Holocaust)—in which victims confront perpetrators: Raya Morag, *Perpetrator Cinema: Confronting Genocide in Cambodian Documentary* (London ; New York: Columbia University Press, 2020).

⁵ Aaron Kerner, *Film and the Holocaust: New Perspectives on Dramas, Documentaries, and Experimental Films* (New York: Continuum, 2011), 15–30.

⁶ James E. Young, *Writing and Rewriting the Holocaust: Narrative and the Consequences of Interpretation* (Indiana UP, 1988), 51.

⁷ Ivone Margulies, *In Person: Reenactment in Postwar and Contemporary Cinema* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2019), 16, 167, doi:10.1093/oso/9780190496821.001.0001.

It is the film's challenge to the boastful and freely embellished perpetrator performances, or the perceived lack thereof that has received the most critical attention, positive or negative. But I believe it has been inadequately framed in terms of the reenactments' supposed fictionality and whether in this light protagonist and perpetrator Anwar Congo's show of remorse at the end of the film is ultimately believable.⁸ For instance, Bill Nichols's review of the film establishes that "[b]efuddlement arises when a clear distinction between fictional and documentary representation fails to materialize" and ultimately concludes that the film "presents a reality that is too thoroughly unbelievable to be true."⁹ In a more condemnatory tone, documentary filmmaker Jill Godmilow claims that after watching the film "we leave the theater with a fantasy degree in Indonesian history".¹⁰ Stefan Iversen and Henrik Skov Nielsen in their positive assessment of the film, in turn, embrace the "fictionality" of its reenactments and assert that the "most important function of the fictionalised scenes thus seems to be to provide evidence as to what actually took place."¹¹ Lúcia Nagib, on the other hand, believes that "the film is entirely

⁸ Lucien van Liere, "The Banality of Ghosts," *Journal for Religion, Film and Media* 4, no. 1 (March 29, 2018): 32, doi:10.25364/05.4:2018.1.2; Mike Meneghetti, "Self-Exculpatory Imaginings: Reenactment and Observation in *The Act of Killing*," *Canadian Journal of Film Studies* 25, no. 2 (October 2016): 46–47, doi:10.3138/cjfs.25.2.39; Adam Tyson, "Genocide Documentary as Intervention," *Journal of Genocide Research* 17, no. 2 (April 3, 2015): 191, doi:10.1080/14623528.2015.1027077; Warren Crichtlow, "'It's All About Finding the Right Excuse' in Joshua Oppenheimer's *The Act of Killing*," *Film Quarterly* 67, no. 2 (December 2013): 37–43, doi:10.1525/fq.2014.67.2.37; Nick Fraser, "We Love Impunity: The Case of 'The Act of Killing,'" *Film Quarterly* 67, no. 2 (December 2013): 21–24, doi:10.1525/fq.2014.67.2.21.

⁹ Bill Nichols, "Irony, Cruelty, Evil (and a Wink) in 'The Act of Killing,'" *Film Quarterly* 67, no. 2 (December 2013): 25 & 29, doi:10.1525/fq.2014.67.2.25.

¹⁰ Jill Godmilow, "Killing the Documentary: An Oscar-Nominated Filmmaker Takes Issue With 'The Act of Killing,'" *IndieWire*, March 5, 2014, <https://www.indiewire.com/2014/03/killing-the-documentary-an-oscar-nominated-filmmaker-takes-issue-with-the-act-of-killing-29332/>. Oppenheimer himself avows that his film is "a documentary of the imagination." Joshua Oppenheimer, "Promotional Booklet for *The Act of Killing* / *The Look of Silence*" (Dogwoof, October 12, 2015).

¹¹ Stefan Iversen and Henrik Skov Nielsen, "The Politics of Fictionality in Documentary Form: The Act of Killing and The Ambassador," *European Journal of English Studies* 20, no. 3 (September 1, 2016): 257, doi:10.1080/13825577.2016.1230389.

structured on the principle of systematically preventing the formation of a plausible fictional or narrative world in the name of the reality of the profilmic event.”¹²

As these incongruous views suggest, the question of the boundary between fiction and non-fiction seems to be at the center of the film. This, however, poses some significant problems for its status as documentary. If fictionality is the film’s most salient feature, what does it document? And how does it document? While Nielsen and Iversen, echoing a position more widely held in narratology,¹³ take it for granted that fictionality can communicate actual knowledge across the abyss of make-believe, pretense, or non-actuality, the philosophical literature—which arguably tackles this problem with more analytical precision—is much less straightforward on the issue of “truth through fiction.”¹⁴ If the reenactments are fictional, and thus require that the audience suspend their belief, how do they impart knowledge to us, which in turn would require us to believe?¹⁵ The dominant focus on fictionality in TAOK faces another issue: the vast majority of reenactments—excepting a few scenes in which we encounter entities or acts we know impossible to have actually been captured on camera (a ghost from Congo’s dreams; a scene set in heaven; Congo’s severed head eating liver)—are not fictional.¹⁶ In characterizing the

¹² Lúcia Nagib, “Regurgitated Bodies. Presenting and Representing Trauma in *The Act of Killing*,” in *The Routledge Companion to Cinema and Politics*, ed. Yannis Tzioumakis and Claire Molloy (Routledge, 2016), 221. For a further source framing the film in terms of fiction vs nonfiction, see Cristina Demaria and Patrizia Violi, “The Act of Documenting: Joshua Oppenheimer’s *The Act of Killing*,” *Media, War & Conflict* 13, no. 1 (March 1, 2020): 5–7, doi:10.1177/1750635219871910.

¹³ See the second and eighth thesis in: Henrik Skov Nielsen, James Phelan, and Richard Walsh, “Ten Theses about Fictionality,” *Narrative* 23, no. 1 (2015): 64, doi:10.1353/nar.2015.0005.

¹⁴ For an overview, see the corresponding chapter in: Fred Kroon and Alberto Voltolini, “Fiction,” in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, ed. Edward N. Zalta, Winter 2019 (Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, 2019), <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2019/entries/fiction/>.

¹⁵ Most accounts of knowledge characterize it in terms of belief, see Jonathan Jenkins Ichikawa and Matthias Steup, “The Analysis of Knowledge,” in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, ed. Edward N. Zalta, Summer 2018 (Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, 2018), <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2018/entries/knowledge-analysis/>.

¹⁶ Mario Slugan, “Textualism, Extratextualism, and the Fiction/Nonfiction Distinction in Documentary Studies,” *Studies in Documentary Film* 15, no. 2 (May 4, 2021): 116–17, doi:10.1080/17503280.2021.1923142.

reenactments as fictional, many critics tacitly conflate the two very different ontologies of representations of actual events with representations of non-actual, i.e. fictional, events. Surely, there can be no doubt that the killers' reenactments of their past deeds, with or without donned cowboy hats, are the former and not the latter—in fact, the film's entire premise depends on a common agreement between film crew, perpetrators, and audience that the vast majority of reenactments are non-fictional.

In the following, I will seek to reframe the discussion about fictionality in TAOK in terms of unreliable narration. This has several advantages. We can avoid the problems associated with fictionality posed above, since most reenactments are not fictional to begin with and my arguments will not depend on making a case about their respective non/fictionality. Instead, I will focus on the narratological complexities of the film and its implications for the film's narrative ethics. The ethical and narratological problems posed by the film cut across its fictional and non-fictional segments: we face the same fundamental ethical question, whether perpetrators reenact their (actual, historical) killings or when perpetrator Congo creates and films an entirely fictional scene of being thanked by his victims for killing and sending them to heaven. The problem is less in the reenactments' occasional aesthetical flourish of a Wild West or neo-noir Mafia film, however distasteful that may be, and more so in what these stylized tellings are symptoms of: the perpetrators control the narrative and revisit their past with relish and in public. It is the boastful tone of their narratives of murder which makes them unreliable, and they are unreliable predominantly in ethical terms, not with regard to their supposed fictionality. We know (and the perpetrators want us to know) that the killings in the reenactments happened and the fictional scenes make no attempt at masquerading as actuality. Fictional and non-fictional

scenes are not unreliable on the axis of fact, they are ultimately and predominantly unreliable on the axis of ethics.

My argument proceeds in three stages: first, I will discuss various forms of unreliability in narrative as well as briefly outline the distinction between *histoire* and *discours* which is needed to distinguish the narrative levels of the film. Second, I will discuss how these forms of unreliability play out in the film's perpetrator narratives and how the film's overall *discours* counteracts them. Finally, I will seek to specifically reassess the film's framing of perpetrator Congo as a narrator whose apparent change of conscience throughout the film particularly dominates (especially in more skeptical or downright negative) critiques of the film.¹⁷

Unreliability and narration

The narrative situation in TAOK is somewhat more complicated than most documentaries. The film has a top-level instance of narration, which I will call L1 for purposes of disambiguation. This is the film Oppenheimer and his largely anonymous Indonesian crew let us see. But within L1, we also encounter sub-level narration, narrators, and characters in the form of the perpetrators, which I will call L2. The perpetrators are characters in their own reenactments (i.e. narratives), but the overall film's narration also lets us encounter the perpetrators as narrators of their narratives, giving us insight in turn into their modes of narration. It is here, at these sub-levels of narration (L2) where, or so I will argue, we encounter unreliability from the vantage point of the film's overall narration (L1).

¹⁷ van Liere, "The Banality of Ghosts"; Meneghetti, "Self-Exculpatory Imaginings"; Tyson, "Genocide Documentary as Intervention"; Crichlow, "'It's All About Finding the Right Excuse' in Joshua Oppenheimer's *The Act of Killing*."

While omissions and incomplete information characterize all narration, what marks a narration unreliable is when it “does not communicate to spectators that some important information is hidden or concealed.”¹⁸ It is up to the viewer to evaluate the degree of reliability of the account offered by unreliable narration, to demarcate its gaps, and perhaps to complete it. Crucially, there are several ways in which we can encounter unreliability that are not simply reducible to whether or not the information about *events* in the narrative(s) is truthful. James Phelan distinguishes between three axes on which unreliability may occur in written fiction, which are applicable to nonfictional works as well: the axes of events, ethics, and “knowledge/perception.”¹⁹ All three axes, as we will see, play a role in the unreliable narration of perpetrators, and remarkably they are the least unreliable (though unreliable still) when it comes to the conveyance of historical information—the axis of events and facts. More significant is the perpetrator-narrators’ *perception* and ethical *evaluation* of the narrated events, and it is here we find the highest degree of unreliability.²⁰ Perpetrator-narrator Anwar Congo’s pink cowboy hat, donned in his Western-style reenactments of killings, constitutes only a minor change in his recounting of his deeds (the axis of events) compared to the historical facts. Yet, his donning of various costumes from entertainment films, including cowboy hats, betrays a major ethical disregard for his victims—killed again for the camera, this time with a dash more color and self-congratulatory bravado—and at the same time reveals an understanding of history (this, too, is ultimately an ethical

¹⁸ Warren Buckland, *Narrative and Narration: Analyzing Cinematic Storytelling, Narrative and Narration* (Columbia UP, 2020), 95, doi:10.7312/buck18143.

¹⁹ James Phelan, *Living to Tell about It: A Rhetoric and Ethics of Character Narration* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2004), 34–35.

²⁰ I should mention here that, based on these three axes, Phelan distinguishes between a total of six kinds of unreliability: misreporting and underreporting (on the axis of events), misreading and underreading (on the axis of perception and knowledge), as well as misregarding and underregarding (on the axis of ethics). The difference between the prefixes “mis-” and “under-” is to do with the degree of unreliability on the respective axis, where “mis-” characterizes a greater degree of unreliability than “under-”. Given the blatant unreliability of the perpetrator-narrators, I don’t think it necessary to include these fine nuances in my account of unreliability here, and I will focus on the distinction of unreliability between the axes rather than within them. *Ibid.*, 51–52.

disregard) as being representable according to his whim and pleasure (axes of perception and ethics). Indeed, that his unreliability proceeds more along the axes of ethics and perception than that of events—Congo does not seek to minimize his involvement in the killings—can be taken as yet further indication for a blatant lack of moral compass.

What marks out a narrative as unreliable, of course, can only be measured against a certain foundation which serves as a yardstick of reliability for the audience. Depending on the axis, that foundation can differ. No doubt, the narrative axis of events should be measured against whether the events actually took place in the way they are narrated. In the case of documentary, the audience has an easier job than in the case of (especially non-historical) fiction—where factually unreliable narrators often require careful parsing by the audience for what’s left out, distorted, or skipped—since the audience can often draw on at least partial historical records or accounts independent of the documentary’s own narration of events. TAOK provides such a basic factual backdrop even for (most likely) uninitiated Western audiences—including a brief summary of the killings, the perpetrators’ present-day impunity, and that the following documentary will feature their reenactments of killings—in a title card at the beginning of the documentary. However, the documentary is less about facts, even less so about historical facts, and the claim that we are left with a “fantasy degree in Indonesian history” misses the mark.²¹ The brief historical facts provided by the documentary serve, rather, as a factual bedrock that in turn is to facilitate the viewer’s

²¹ Godmilow, “Killing the Documentary.” Other criticism of *The Act of Killing* on a factual basis seems to be in part derived from a more general, reductive understanding of the documentary medium. Thus, Fraser asserts that for documentary films “it is good to be literal and truthful,” implying that *The Act of Killing* is not. Fraser, “We Love Impunity,” 22. In a similar vein, Tyson charges the film for heavily featuring perpetrator Congo’s “foggy recollections” and their “anecdotal” evidence and that the film in fact did not feature a representative and large enough sample of perpetrators, as if the documentary should be judged by methods from social sciences or academic history. Tyson, “Genocide Documentary as Intervention,” 182–84. Measured in this way, nearly all documentaries would have to fall short and rather than, say, watch *Shoah*, one should read Hilberg’s monumental *The Destruction of the European Jews*.

reflecting on the perpetrators' ethics and perception of history and what these tell us about the Indonesian engagement with its violent past more generally. In short, the film's point is precisely about the perpetrators' (and Indonesian society's) unreliability on the axes of perception and ethics. On these axes, too, what counts as unreliable is measured against a yardstick. At its heart lies the fundamental and perhaps universal assumption that killing unarmed civilians and boasting about it is ethically reprehensible. While the film makes this general, basic assumption largely tacitly, its overall narration (L1) contravenes that of the perpetrators (L2) particularly with respect to their narrative ethics and perception in several subtle but explicit ways that mark the perpetrator narratives as unreliable.²² My argument will focus on the film's interventions in the perpetrators' narration.

But before we can proceed to a closer examination of the film, I need to establish a final, well-known distinction: that between *histoire* (or also *fabula*, story) and *discours* (or also discourse, *syuzhet*, plot).²³ *Discours* denotes the representation, organized in particular narrative ways (as linear narrative, via flashbacks or flashforwards, etc.), of an underlying story that provides, as it were, the raw material, the *histoire* (which in turn provides, say, the chronological basis against which we can judge a flashback as being a flashback).²⁴ What is immediately apparent in TAOK is its explicitness and self-reflexivity about its *discours*, that is, its narrative organization

²² The film thus shares this assumption with fictional works written from the internal narrative perspective of genocidal perpetrators. On this tacit assumption of a cultural context that condemns genocide as well as the potential dangers of ideological identification with the perpetrators on part of the viewer, see Erin McGlothlin, "Empathetic Identification and the Mind of the Holocaust Perpetrator in Fiction: A Proposed Taxonomy of Response," *Narrative* 24, no. 3 (2016): 265, doi:10.1353/nar.2016.0016. Nonetheless, *The Act of Killing* makes arguably fewer demands on the viewer to carefully parse for the ethical position of the implied "author" (Oppenheimer and his crew) and detect the perpetrators' narrational unreliability than said perpetrator fiction, which can get away with being less explicit in its condemnation of its subjects due to its focus on the Holocaust as the most known and comprehensively condemned genocide ("the crime of the century", "the worst crime in human history" etc.).

²³ For my purposes here, the differences between, say, *histoire*, *fabula*, and story are not of interest.

²⁴ The literature on this distinction is immense. For a recent discussion with regard to film, see Buckland, *Narrative and Narration*.

of an underlying *histoire*. The underlying *histoire* of the overall film (L1), in turn, is predominantly constituted by the perpetrators' narratives of their deeds and discussions about how to narrate them (L2). Its primary focus is not the history of the killings itself. The perpetrators' discussions and narrative implementations (in their reenactments) of this 'how' to narrate their deeds is in turn itself a *discours*. The film's conundrum is that the narrative ethical purpose of its *discours* (L1) is at odds with that of the perpetrators' *discours* (L2). Thus, the film has to be so explicit about its discursiveness, because it is precisely its self-reflexivity about its *discours*—through editing, use of offscreen space, and the interventions of Oppenheimer's voice and cameras into the narrative *discours* of the perpetrators—that marks the perpetrators' *discours* as unreliable.

Perpetrator *histoire* and propaganda

In order to understand the film's own (L1) narrative intervention into the perpetrators' *discours* we first need to understand the perpetrators' various *histoires* and their contexts. The most obvious *histoire* is their historical background as killers and torturers. Other elements of the perpetrators' *histoires* are more difficult to discern independently of the film's overall *discours* (L1), in part because the film has thoroughly reframed the perpetrators' narratives and because they stem from Indonesian anti-communist propaganda contexts and national narratives.

Suharto's New Order propaganda of supposed murderous communist excesses served as a justification for the rightwing massacres in 1965-66 of supposed communists, union members, and feminists and still perpetuates the current impunity of and power abuses by the perpetrators

so visible throughout the film (L1).²⁵ The regime elaborately propagated a negative image of these groups in its museums, monuments, history books, and most importantly films.²⁶ The most prominent propaganda product of the regime, scenes of which we also see in the director's cut in TAOK,²⁷ is the propaganda film *Pengkhianatan Gerakan 30 September/PKI (Treachery of the 30th September Movement/Indonesian Communist Party; 1984)*. This film develops a "master narrative" of the "innocent, apolitical and noncommunist" army generals who were murdered by supposed communists in 1965, which in turn sparked the anti-communist massacres organized by the Suharto New Order.²⁸ The propaganda film's influence on Indonesians' reception of the history of the killings can hardly be overestimated. In 2000, the Indonesian weekly *Tempo* held a survey "canvassing 1,101 secondary school students from the nation's three largest cities (Jakarta, Surabaya and Medan). To the question of where they had learned the history of the 1965 events, 90 per cent responded 'film'. As there was only one film on the

²⁵ I agree with Wieringa's criticism here that TAOK could have made it clearer how the perpetrators' own gender politics (their misogyny is unambiguous and omnipresent throughout the film) connects to the Indonesian New Order's violent repression of the feminist Gerwani movement. S. E. Wieringa, "Sexual Slander Revealed: The Story of Jamilah/Jemilah and The Act of Killing," *Indonesian Feminist Journal* 3 (August 2015): 20–21, <https://dare.uva.nl/search?identifier=06767f75-4f26-4704-8cd3-b02dbc279e72>. The gendered dimension of the 1965-66 massacres is more apparent in Maj Wechselmann's near contemporaneous documentary: Maj Wechselmann, *The Women and the Generals*, Documentary (Swedish Television (SvT)/Norwegian Broadcasting (NRK)/Fritt Ord (Norway), 2013), <https://vimeo.com/119472614>. The anti-feminist discourse of emasculating communist Gerwani women sexually mutilating innocent army generals is vividly present in the Indonesian propaganda film *Pengkhianatan Gerakan 30 September/PKI*, see Katharine E. McGregor, *History in Uniform: Military Ideology and the Construction of Indonesia's Past* (NUS Press, 2007), 100; Wieringa, "Sexual Slander Revealed." The Museum Pengkhianatan PKI ("betrayal of the Indonesian Communist Party") repeats and restages these myths which the West happily gobbled up at the time, see S. Wieringa, *Sexual Politics in Indonesia* (Houndmills, Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2002), 320–21.

²⁶ For an extensive account of this construction of the past, see McGregor, *History in Uniform*; Saskia E. Wieringa and Nursyahbani Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia: Imagined Evil* (New York, NY: Routledge, 2019), esp. introduction.

²⁷ There are two releases of the film, the cinematic and the director's cut. The cinematic release of the film does not feature excerpts from the propaganda film and the discussion between Congo and fellow perpetrator Adi Zulkadry about the film's lack of truthfulness is left out as well. I discuss both cuts here and will make it clear throughout the text which cut I am talking about if a scene is not present in both.

²⁸ Ariel Heryanto, "Screening the 1965 Violence," in *Killer Images: Documentary Film, Memory and the Performance of Violence*, ed. Joram Ten Brink and Joshua Oppenheimer (Boston, MA: Wallflower Press, 2012), 15.

subject, there is no ambiguity as to which film they were referring to; as many as 97 per cent said they had seen the film *Pengkhianatan G 30 September*.”²⁹

The perpetrators’ fictional story of *Arsan dan Aminah* (Arsan and Aminah) takes inspiration from these propagandistic contexts. The story is about Arsan, a rightwing man played by perpetrator Anwar Congo, and Aminah, his communist girlfriend “played by his potbellied assistant Herman [Koto] in grotesque drag.”³⁰ Arsan is eventually murdered and mutilated by his maniacally screaming girlfriend who feeds Arsan’s liver to his severed head in a form of emasculating gesture.³¹ Even though a few of the scenes of *Arsan dan Aminah* feature relatively prominently in TAOK, the film was never fully thought out as a feature and it was always clear to all parties involved that the perpetrators would be shooting merely a few exemplary scenes from this supposed film.³² The fact that TAOK does not feature very much of the *Arsan dan Aminah* narrative is precisely owing to the fact that the film does not subscribe to this narrative with its predominantly justificatory purpose and instead opts to focus on the perpetrators’ own *discours* of their historical deeds, whose self-celebratory nature is nonetheless derived from the propagandistic contexts provided by the former New Order.

The perpetrators’ enthusiastic embrace of reenactments as a way to perform their history, in turn, is most likely not only inspired by the glitzy flair of Hollywood films, but also by similar traditions of performative history under the New Order regime, which encouraged its population to stage reenactments of the killings of the generals.³³ For instance, the dialogue script for a

²⁹ Ibid., 224.

³⁰ Wieringa, “Sexual Slander Revealed,” 19.

³¹ Ibid., 20.

³² “On Anwar, from Oppenheimer,” *Caroline M Cooper*, June 13, 2013, <https://carolinemcooper.com/on-anwar-from-oppenheimer/>.

³³ I am thus quite doubtful about Meneghetti’s claim that Oppenheimer “has framed [the film’s] reception for Western audiences.” Meneghetti, “Self-Exculpatory Imaginings”, note 8. In a sense, it speaks to Meneghetti’s own situatedness within Western discourses if he only reads the film in reference to “longstanding polemical dialogues

primary school class play in which the students are asked to play communists torturing the generals reads: “‘Kill him, kill him’, ‘Cut up his flesh’, ‘crush his head’, ‘Cut off his tongue and his hands’ [...]. Accompanying instructions suggested those in the role of the PKI [Indonesian Communist Party] should have replica weapons and mime the beating of the ‘good’ generals.”³⁴ What the New Order regime does not reenact or represent, however, is the violence and the scale thereof against supposed communists that ensued after the killing of the generals—and herein lies a crucial difference to the perpetrators’ reenactments of their own deeds.

These wider Indonesian historical narratives graft a significant amount of fiction—communists as brutal murderers and sexual abusers of army generals and, symbolically, Indonesian society more generally—onto an actual event—a poorly bungled coup attempt by a left-leaning splinter group in the military in coordination with some civilian leaders among which were PKI.³⁵ The connection of the perpetrators’ views to the propaganda film and the perpetrators’ overall support by Indonesian officials, ranging from Indonesian National Television to then governor of North Sumatra Syamsul Arifin, are apparent in TAOK. Yet, remarkably, unlike the state propaganda film, the majority of the perpetrators’ reenactments themselves never need to resort to such fictionalizing leaps, since the majority of their reenactments is in fact not constituted by the fictional *Arsan dan Aminah* story but rather the perpetrators’ own—historical—deeds. It is not least the brutal facticity of the perpetrators’ reenactments that makes them so outrageous. The violent excesses—if perhaps not in all their details, then at least so in the *type* of violence they demonstrate—are all too real. Thus, even

within the history of Western documentary filmmaking” (ibid.) without considering any Indonesian media and propagandistic contexts.

³⁴ McGregor, *History in Uniform*, 102.

³⁵ John Roosa, *Pretext for Mass Murder: The September 30th Movement and Suharto’s Coup D’État in Indonesia* (Madison, Wis: University of Wisconsin Press, 2006), 22, 41–47. Roosa estimates the movement to be in total about 4130 personnel strong, 46.

though the perpetrators pursue the same self-justificatory goals in their reenactments as the New Order propaganda, they are less successful in part precisely because the crucial justification for the vast scale of the massacres in the Indonesian propaganda lies in the propaganda's inculcating of all communists for their cruelty, whereas the perpetrators' reenactments of their murder of communists demonstrates their very own brutality, and consequently their reenactments inadvertently give "a re-visibility [to] the lost instances of death."³⁶ The propaganda uses fiction to provide a justificatory backdrop for their aggressive anticommunist campaign, which itself is not shown, whereas fictional elements (Cowboy hats or the *Arsan dan Aminah* backstory) in the perpetrators' reenactments ever only act as defensive mechanisms for their *histoire* of murder that is too close to history. In order to dress up—quite literally—their ugly *histoire*, the perpetrators thus have to rely on self-flattering *discours* of their acts. But precisely this *discours* (L2) fails, because the film (L1) frames it as unreliable, as I will explain in the following.

Unreliability and two levels of *discours*

In narrative contexts that assume an audience (as Oppenheimer's film does) which condemns the torture and killings of unarmed civilians, the perpetrators' *histoire* alone would already go a long way towards the audience's condemnation of the perpetrators' actions.³⁷ Nonetheless, the film provides a clear frame of reference that shapes the audience response to the perpetrators especially along the axes of perception and ethics beyond a mere passive reliance on the audience's condemnation of mass murder. Through the film's filming of the perpetrators' *discours*, we get insight into the perpetrators' narratives that reveals them as unreliable

³⁶ Elizabeth Wijaya, "To See Die, Again: The Act of Filming and The Act of Killing," *Parallax* 22, no. 1 (January 2, 2016): 83, doi:10.1080/13534645.2015.1135520.

³⁷ McGlothlin, "Empathetic Identification and the Mind of the Holocaust Perpetrator in Fiction," 256. See also above footnote 21.

narrators—and crucially it does so especially in terms of their perception of and moral response to their narratives, not least since, concerning the axis of events, none of the perpetrators' narratives deny the fact that they killed on an extensive scale.³⁸

The contrast of the film's *discours* with that of the perpetrators', revealing the latter to be unreliable, becomes clear in the moments when, in the director's cut, Oppenheimer (offscreen) asks about the propaganda film *Pengkhianatan G30S/PKI*. Perpetrator Adi Zulkadry, who is the most articulate among the perpetrators but also completely inveterate, states outright that "it [the propaganda film] is a lie." But Congo quickly interjects that "We shouldn't say bad things about that film to outsiders," suggesting a double standard as to how the film is perceived and can be discussed among insiders (among perpetrators) as opposed to outsiders (Oppenheimer and the audience of the overall film (L1)). Since the purpose of the propaganda film was to justify the New Order's existence (including the circumstances of its coming into being through mass killings of the communists as its main political rival) and the perpetrators' reenactments seek to fulfill the same purpose, we are already forewarned that the perpetrators' perception of these narratives (official or their own) as false and to be criticized only behind closed doors is at odds with how these narratives themselves demand to be perceived by their audience as glorifying and justificatory. Further ironic contrast is created by the fact that the perpetrators' self-unmasking remarks occur while they are masked up for their reenactments.

The perpetrators' unreliability is revealed even more tellingly in a thematically and chronologically central scene included in both the cinematic release and the director's cut where the perpetrators violate the axis of ethics, and their narrational *discours* (L2) is in stark contrast

³⁸ Throughout the film we only encounter one person denying complicity in or knowledge of the mass murder taking place (in this case on the rooftop of his work place, a newspaper office): the journalist Soadun Siregar.

to that of the film itself (L1): The perpetrators' account of their deeds is missing the victim's perspective. Precisely such a perspective, however, is offered by the film. In what appears to be a break during the perpetrators' filming, Suryono, one of the actors recruited from the perpetrators' community, steps forward and offers his personal experiences of the killings to the perpetrators. Suryono tells the story of the abduction of his stepfather and his hasty burial, once Suryono and his grandfather found the body. He also mentions his and other descendants of victims' forced displacement and subsequent stigmatization. Suryono, laughing uncomfortably, promises repeatedly that he is not criticizing the perpetrators and that he tells the story only as "input for the film," at which point the perpetrators interrupt and state that his story will not be included in their film. The quick dismissal of Suryono's victim's perspective by the perpetrators—a narrative perspective that is incommensurable with their narrative ethics of glorifying violence rather than showing its harrowing consequences—stands in stark juxtaposition by its inclusion in the film's own *discours*.³⁹

Even if Suryono's narrative perspective is excluded from the perpetrators' *discours*, they, of course, have no qualms of including him as victim in narratives centered on themselves. Thus, immediately after Suryono told his story of victimhood to the perpetrators, we watch him play a communist victim in the perpetrators' film,⁴⁰ realizing that the roles of perpetrator and victim have not much changed since the killings. The perpetrators' doubled narrative violence of excluding Suryono's account as well as revictimizing him in their reenactments clearly leaves

³⁹ While TAOK is predominantly focused on the perpetrators (unlike its sequel: Joshua Oppenheimer, *The Look of Silence*, Documentary (Dogwoof, 2014)), Wandita's charge that the story of the victims is "blackened out" is rather uncharitable in light of Suryono's testimony in the film. Galuh Wandita, "'PREMAN' NATION: Watching 'The Act of Killing' in Indonesia," *Critical Asian Studies* 46, no. 1 (January 2, 2014): 169, doi:10.1080/14672715.2014.863585.

⁴⁰ It should be noted that (contrary to the type of victim he plays in the reenactment) Suryono was persecuted for ethnic, not for political reasons (the ethnic dimension of the killings is absent from the perpetrators' re-enactments but briefly acknowledged in the film by Zulkadry).

Suryono traumatized, and he cries long after the reenactment is clearly over. Once more, the perpetrators show no sensibility for the victims' perspective and ignore Suryono's manifest distress. The film's *discours*, however, lingers on Suryono's tears and pained expression, emphasizing what the perpetrators cancel out.⁴¹ Suryono's trauma and the fact that Suryono's story is told—in the film's own *discours*—effectively against the perpetrators' consent, makes the difference between film's own narrative ethics and that of the perpetrators most explicit and highlights their ethical unreliability.

Ironically, it is precisely in the aftermath of Suryono's story and his revictimization in the subsequent reenactment that perpetrator Zulkadry senses a difference in the narrative perception and ethics of the overall film (L1) compared to their own (L2). Oppenheimer's camera captures Zulkadry's expressing doubts to other perpetrators about whether their reenactments will actually end up promoting them and their deeds (he says "it's about image") in the final documentary. Zulkadry thus demonstrates an awareness that the film's *discours* (L1) framing that of the perpetrators (L2) may undermine the audience response sought by the perpetrators' *discours*, while Zulkadry's very awareness in front of Oppenheimer's cameras is itself subject to the scrutiny of the film's audience. Thus, at once, Zulkadry's worries lay bare, *ex negativo*, the underlying ambitions and desires of self-glorification, while his expressing these worries becomes itself the subject of the film's *discours* and is thus immediately denied any success at self-glorification in the eyes of the film's audience that has now become witness to Zulkadry's unwitting self-betrayal.

The self-betrayal also reveals the perpetrators' ethical double standard. When Zulkadry says that the film "will disprove all the propaganda about the communists being cruel and show

⁴¹ Bill Nichols, *Speaking Truths with Film: Evidence, Ethics, Politics in Documentary* (Oakland: University of California Press, 2016), 178.

that we were cruel!” and Congo concurs “We’re the cruel ones,” the perpetrators’ effectively disclose their own contradictory attitude towards their violent past which does not square with their simultaneous intent to prime the response of the audience to their deeds as worthy of glory and praise. Zulkadry’s admission of their cruelty (which also contradicts their later self-presentation of themselves as “humane” killers on Indonesian national television) while also clearly still desiring glorification for their deeds, suggests a duplicitous narrative ethics on part of the perpetrators that finds praise in the cruel.⁴²

An important factor in separating the film’s own *discours* from that of the perpetrators is the use of offscreen space as the space of interrogation and problematization of the perpetrators’ viewpoints. This is particularly noticeable in Oppenheimer’s constant presence in the offscreen space—asking probing questions and repeatedly being referred to by the perpetrators in their various conversations—but visible absence from the diegesis.⁴³ Oppenheimer exists only as audible interrogator functioning as the ethically authoritative voice of the film’s *discours*, resisting any representation onscreen at the same level as the perpetrators. A particularly pertinent example is a scene in which Oppenheimer confronts perpetrator Zulkadry with having committed war crimes. Zulkadry replies that “war crimes are defined by the winners. I am a winner so I can make my own definition.” Oppenheimer reemphasizes the ethics of the film’s *discours* (L1) in contrast to that of the perpetrators, when he evokes human rights and criminal

⁴² My readings of the perpetrators’ perceptual unreliability here are quite close to what Camilla Reestorff calls the perpetrators’ becoming “‘troubled indexes’ of themselves and their past” in those moments in which they acknowledge or even celebrate their violence while also evincing a clear unease about their pasts (e.g. nightmares). Camilla Møhring Reestorff, “Unruly Artivism and the Participatory Documentary Ecology of The Act of Killing,” *Studies in Documentary Film* 9, no. 1 (January 2, 2015): 21, doi:10.1080/17503280.2014.1002248.

⁴³ On the role of Oppenheimer’s voice, see Demaria and Violi, “The Act of Documenting,” 13–15. Nonetheless, I disagree with Demaria and Violi that the film itself offers no “moral evaluation,” lacks a “value frame,” and uses meta-cinematic references in their place (p. 15). Not only is it unclear how such meta-cinematic references can replace a moral value frame if they in turn do not imply a value frame, but the film’s interventions in various forms, including the Oppenheimer’s interrogating the perpetrators from the off, clearly presuppose an ethical value system, as I argue in this article.

justice by asking Zulkadry: “What if you were brought to the international court in The Hague?” Zulkadry cheerfully replies, still pursuing the common perpetrator agenda of self-glorification and in complete contravention of the court’s purpose of upholding human rights: “I’d go! I don’t feel guilty, so why would I go? Because I’d be famous. I’m ready! [He laughs] Please get me called to The Hague!” In making his points, Zulkadry, who is driving, repeatedly looks to the passenger seat of the car, where, presumably, Oppenheimer is sitting. Yet, Oppenheimer, although clearly audible, is situated offscreen and is never seen. This cinematographically enacted barrier between onscreen and offscreen space suggests to us that Zulkadry’s points fail to reach Oppenheimer. Zulkadry is filmed through the back mirror making his arguments, his eyes moving from the road to the passenger seat, but since neither road nor passenger enter the frame, Zulkadry’s gaze never seems to arrive at anyone he could convince—a visual embodiment of his argument’s failure. Offscreen space is thus established as a space that challenges the perpetrators’ narrative perspective.

Congo’s unreliable conscience

The separation between an onscreen space dominated by the perpetrators’ problematic narratives and the film’s own *discours* (L1) enforced from outside the screen also reveals Congo’s troubling relationship with his own identity as a killer and his attempts to come to terms with his deeds. The unreliable, indeed duplicitous perception by Congo of his reenactments is apparent when, in the space of mere minutes, he characterizes them as fact *and* fiction whenever it is convenient for him. Getting his grandchildren out of bed Congo tells them: “watch the scene where grandpa is tortured and killed. [...] Come see grandpa beaten up and bleeding.” Oppenheimer objects repeatedly from outside the screen that “this is too violent,” upon which

Congo replies “This is only a film.” Just moments later when finished watching the scene in which he had played a victim, Congo states that he can feel what his victims felt. Congo’s awakening of conscience relies on the erasure between the boundary of fact and fiction in order to suppose an equivalence between his own fictional victimhood and the nonfictional victimhood of his victims. However, Congo had reasserted precisely this boundary when he brushed away Oppenheimer’s concern that the violence of the reenactment might traumatize Congo’s grandchildren. Once more, the offscreen functions as a space from which the film establishes the difference on the axis of perception and, ultimately, ethics in its *discours* to the perpetrator-narrators’ when Oppenheimer interjects that his victims felt far worse because they knew they were dying, whereas Congo was merely playacting. More paradoxically yet, Congo’s very ability to empathize with his victims is in fact dependent on a tacit reestablishment of the boundary between fact and fiction, Oppenheimer reminds us, because unlike his victims, Congo was able to survive his own, merely cinematic, death.

Questions of reliability are also raised in the film’s final and perhaps most famous scene: Congo’s redemption on the rooftop where he committed many of his murders. Since many critics deem it central, so central in fact that the film’s overall merit supposedly hinges on the scene’s success, it deserves especially close attention. Meneghetti, for example, argues that the film’s success depends on Congo’s “protracted paroxysms and penitence [... as] keys to *The Act of Killing*’s purported moral demonstration.”⁴⁴ Crichlow, in a similar vein, states that “the film predicates its moral insight on Anwar’s losing battle to defend against the terrorizing truth [of his deeds],”⁴⁵ and van Liere maintains that the film pursues a soteriological plot culminating in

⁴⁴ Meneghetti, “Self-Exculpatory Imaginings,” 40.

⁴⁵ Crichlow, “It’s All About Finding the Right Excuse’ in Joshua Oppenheimer’s *The Act of Killing*,” 40–41.

Congo's seeming show of guilt.⁴⁶ In this light, the success of the film depends, first, on whether its culmination in a scene of supposed redemption is appropriate and, second, the believability of that redemption.⁴⁷ The film's focus on Congo is, no doubt, owing to his greater psychological complexity and ambivalence towards his own actions compared to the coolly rationalizing Zulkadry (whose unreliability is examined throughout the film nonetheless) or the psychological simpleton that is child-rapist Safit Pardede (who would only offer the common platitude of genocidal perpetrators as evil other). And yet, I believe critics' focus on Congo's supposed redemption misunderstands the film, because it fails to notice the film's markers of Congo's unreliability.

The very fact that Congo "deems it necessary to perform somatic affects and grief" already does not square with the perpetrators' otherwise self-congratulatory attitude to their pasts shown previously in the film and demonstrates their unreliable perception of their violence.⁴⁸

Furthermore, the film does not simply accept Congo's demonstration of penitence on the rooftop

⁴⁶ van Liere, "The Banality of Ghosts," 28–29. Further criticism, not exclusively negative, focuses on this scene: Heather McIntosh, "Reenactments and the Denial of Catharsis in *The Act of Killing*," *Quarterly Review of Film and Video* 34, no. 5 (July 4, 2017): 379–94, doi:10.1080/10509208.2016.1144041; Katharina von Kellenbach, "Rituals of Repentance: Joshua Oppenheimer's *The Act of Killing*," in *Guilt: A Force of Cultural Transformation*, ed. Katharina von Kellenbach and Matthias Buschmeier (New York City: OUP, 2021), 185–204; Saira Mohamed, "Of Monsters and Men: Perpetrator Trauma and Mass Atrocity," *Columbia Law Review* 115, no. 5 (2015): 1157–1216; Robert Cribb, "The Act of Killing," *Critical Asian Studies* 46, no. 1 (January 2, 2014): 147–48, doi:10.1080/14672715.2014.867621; Tyson, "Genocide Documentary as Intervention," 191.

⁴⁷ Given this interpretive attitude, those most critical of the film first give much weight to this scene in an assessment of the film's overall success and then consequently doubt that Congo is truly remorseful: Meneghetti, "Self-Exculpatory Imaginings," 46; Cribb, "The Act of Killing," 148; Godmilow, "Killing the Documentary"; (although Tyson's criticism is less dependent on the evaluation of this scene, he too doubts its truthfulness): Tyson, "Genocide Documentary as Intervention," 191. Interestingly, these critics' view is not shared by audiences, as Hill demonstrates in her assessment of international audience responses to TAOK, who were left frustrated by the ending's lack of resolution and believable remorsefulness on part of Congo, despite the fact that some audience members explicitly desired a redemption story, which critics like Meneghetti claim the film foists onto an ugly reality of impunity: Annette Hill, "Documentary Imaginary: Production and Audience Research of *The Act of Killing* and *The Look of Silence*," *European Journal of Cultural Studies* 24, no. 4 (August 1, 2021): 807–11, doi:10.1177/13675494211033291.

⁴⁸ Reestorff, "Unruly Artivism and the Participatory Documentary Ecology of *The Act of Killing*," 24–25.

and in fact juxtaposes, via editing, two scenes of redemption that are entirely incommensurable.⁴⁹ The final chapter in which the rooftop scene is featured is opened (in both cinematic and director's cut) by a preposterously staged scene in heaven in which his victims decorate him with a medal and thank him for killing and sending them to heaven. Then we watch Congo watching this scene, clearly moved by the splendor of his creation. Congo's imagined redemption in heaven, re-confirmed even in the more self-reflexive mode of his watching the scene, then creates a crass contrast to the scene of his redemption on the rooftop, following soon thereafter, during which he retches in seeming repulsion over his past deeds. The two scenes are so jarring, because their redemptive purposes are contradictory: in his imagined heaven, Congo's deeds are not so much *redeemed* as they are deemed praiseworthy by those who suffered most from them, whereas the redeeming elements of Congo's rooftop show of remorse are constituted by his demonstrative awareness of having done wrong. What are we to believe is Congo's view on his murderous past? That it is glorious or regrettable?

The scene of heavenly redemption is also particularly revelatory in itself, not because it is fictional (a heavenly scene in which victims condemned Congo would be equally fictional), but for what it reveals about Congo's, and more generally the perpetrators', attitudes towards their deeds. The scene acknowledges that, contrary to the New Order anti-communist propaganda used to justify the massacres, the victims could not have been so evil for otherwise they would not be in heaven, while it simultaneously also continues the New Order political stance that the killers are praiseworthy. Apart from its revelations about Congo's perceptual unreliability, the scene also betrays Congo's ethical unreliability. The heavenly self-congratulation revictimizes

⁴⁹ The film's main editor Niels Andersen sees the film, much as myself, as focused on the "mechanisms of deceitful storytelling"—a fitting assessment given the important role of editing in showing Congo's unreliability in this scene which is so central to the overall film. Niels Pagh Andersen, *Order in Chaos: Storytelling and Editing in Documentary Film*, trans. Kenny Sanders (Odder, Denmark: Narayana Press, 2021), 115.

the victims on a scale we have not witnessed before in the film. These heavenly victims are not pleading for their lives or resisting the perpetrators' attacks (given that they are already dead), nor are they merely pliant. Instead, they parrot the perpetrators' own ideology and are thereby effectively stripped of their very identity as victims. The consequence of Congo's narrative is effectively that his perpetration of genocide was a victimless crime.

This scene, and its unreliability, is critical for a full understanding of the film, not least because it structures the film. It opens the film, recurs in a short excerpt at the film's midpoint (in the cinematic cut also once more about a third into the film), and is finally and quasi-climactically seen in full (in both cuts) at the opening of the film's final chapter before—in the director's cut—closing the film after Congo's rooftop tears. Congo's imagined heaven is hence established as an important interpretive frame through which we are to see the perpetrators' narratives. The scene's recurrence at the very end in the director's cut gives the film a cyclical structure, carrying the audience back to the beginning and suggesting that we are caught in a continuous retelling of the perpetrators' glorification of their deeds, in turn throwing into critical relief the seemingly linear progression from Congo's first rooftop visit early in the film, during which he cheerfully demonstrates his methods of killing by wire, and his display of remorse during his second at the end.⁵⁰ Thus, instead of an uncritical redemption plot, what TAOK documents is the repeated miscarriage of cathartic narratives that are perhaps at their most contorted and unreliable precisely in Congo's two incommensurable demonstrations of

⁵⁰ Few critics seem to have noticed the return of Congo's paradisiacal redemption scene at the end of the director's cut following his supposed rooftop redemption. Mohamed is an important exception: "At the end of the film, Anwar Congo has not taken full responsibility for his crimes [...] [W]e see his attempt at catharsis fail: There is nothing there. The film closes with another glimpse of Anwar's bizarre redemption fantasy: giant fish, blue skies, green grass." Mohamed, "OF MONSTERS AND MEN," 1199.

redemption.⁵¹ What the film shows, thus, is the perpetrators' continuing power to retell, perceive, and evaluate their actions whichever way they please—a power that extends even beyond the film's *discours*: when the credits roll, the Indonesian members of the film crew remain anonymous for their own safety.

Conclusion

What is so shocking about *The Act of Killing* is the perpetrators' attitudes towards their deeds and their gleeful willingness to discuss and depict them openly. This is not how we encounter genocidal perpetrators in other documentaries. They are usually filmed in the comfort and security of private chambers—guarded from the view of the public—where we may get a limited admission of their culpability (see e.g. the secret footage of perpetrators in Lanzmann's *Shoah*, Prazan's *Einsatzgruppen*, or the private interviews in Holland's *Final Account*),⁵² or we encounter them in judicial or parajudicial contexts,⁵³ confronted by victims, often with various degrees of denial of guilt (Fechner's *Der Prozess*, Panh's *S21* and *Duch*, Chan and Suon's *Red Wedding*, Sambath and Lemkin's *Enemies of the People*, and Aghion's *Mon Voisin, Mon Tueur*).⁵⁴ TAOK's perpetrators, however, are not filmed in private or court rooms and there is no need for secret cameras. They don't deny or diminish their involvement in mass killings. When given a free hand at reenacting their past they don't choose narratives that minimize their role in

⁵¹ For a different reading of the denial of catharsis in TAOK, see: McIntosh, "Reenactments and the Denial of Catharsis in *The Act of Killing*."

⁵² Claude Lanzmann, *Shoah*, Documentary (Les Films Aleph, 1985); Luke Holland, *Final Account*, Documentary (Focus Features, 2021); Michaël Prazan, *Einsatzgruppen: The Nazi Death Squads*, Documentary, (2009).

⁵³ Margulies, *In Person*, 183–218.

⁵⁴ Eberhard Fechner, *Der Prozess*, Documentary (NDR, 1984); Rithy Panh, *S21, la machine de mort khmère rouge*, Documentary (Institut national de l'audiovisuel, 2003); Rithy Panh, *Duch, le maître des forges de l'enfer*, Documentary (Les Acacias, 2012); Linda Chan and Guillaume Suon, *Red Wedding* (Bophana, 2012); Thet Sambath and Rob Lemkin, *Enemies of the People* (International Film Circuit, 2009); Anne Aghion, *Mon Voisin, Mon Tueur* (Gacaca Productions, 2009).

the killings, but instead reenact them with gore and glee using film genres from Hollywood's entertainment industry. Under these circumstances, Oppenheimer and his crew needed to resort to new narrative strategies in order to counteract the perpetrators' narrative *discours*, that is, how they reenact and their discussions about the reenactments. Oppenheimer's objections from outside the screen to the perpetrators' views on their acts, his own camera recording the cameras of the perpetrators, capturing the omissions of victim narratives from their own, and the juxtaposition of perpetrators' unreliable attitudes through the film's editing (L1) continually remind the viewer of an ethical standpoint that takes issue with the perpetrators' views. Since film footage "ha[s] a communicative life that in part escapes the intentions of the filmmaker(s),"⁵⁵ the film's own *discours* can reframe that of the perpetrators and turn it against them to reveal their contradictory assertions and assumptions.

Even though, undoubtedly, the perpetrators are the protagonists of Oppenheimer's documentary, TAOK's shocking and unconventional approach also invites broader consideration of how Indonesia has engaged with its past. Throughout the film, we see the perpetrators getting private audiences with governors, being visited by ministers at reenactment sets, receiving praise from then Indonesian vice president Jusuf Kalla, brazenly and publicly extorting street vendors for money, participating in parades of paramilitary organizations that were involved in the killings and still continue to exert their militant powers, and being celebrated on National Television. Given the perpetrators' integration into Indonesian public and political society as well as into official historical narratives, the film suggests their unreliability extends to Indonesian society more generally. Even today, in 2017, Indonesian President Joko Widodo suggested that if

⁵⁵ Carl Plantinga, "What a Documentary Is, After All," *The Journal of Aesthetics and Art Criticism* 63, no. 2 (2005): 110, doi:10.1111/j.0021-8529.2005.00188.x.

the Indonesian Communist Party revives “just beat them up,”⁵⁶ and the members of the International People’s Tribunal on the 1965 Crimes against Humanity were attacked as “traitors to the nation.”⁵⁷ TAOK does not leave us with a “fantasy degree in Indonesian history.” Rather it exposes the fantastic brutality of Indonesian history as seen through the eyes of the perpetrators. Exposing the perpetrators as unreliable narrators is precisely how Oppenheimer can show the deeply troubling ethics of these narratives.

Yet, TAOK not merely problematizes Indonesian narratives. The perpetrators’ use of Hollywood genres in their reenactment not only casts a problematic light on their attitudes to their pasts, but the ease with which stories of genocidal perpetration can be remolded into casual Hollywood film violence (not least given that the method of killing by wire was inspired by Hollywood gangster films) should give us pause about the ethics of the narratives we make and consume ourselves.

⁵⁶ Wieringa and Katjasungkana, *Propaganda and the Genocide in Indonesia*, 2.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*, 12. Given these contexts, including the propagandistic contexts outlined earlier in this article, Tyson’s assertion that “there is no national silence” seems nigh on cynical. Tyson, “Genocide Documentary as Intervention,” 183.